

Seasonal Variations of Some Phytoplanktonic Algae Collected From Ganga River of Prayagraj District

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Abstract

The phytoplankton forms a very important component of aquatic vegetation, occurring in all kinds of water bodies and consequently enjoying a worldwide distribution. The present study is going to centralize on the Ganga River of Allahabad district in Uttar Pradesh in year 2021-22. The phytoplankton and filamentous, algae were collected, and identified by Prescott (1969), Fritch (1916) fresh water biology. Although, there are a number of major groups of phytoplankton, those relevant to the present study are Bacillariophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Cyanophyceae and Euglenophyceae were identified. Few species of phytoplankton have been collected from the freshwater of Ganga river in the genera Bacillariophyceae, Cyanophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Euglenophyceae from Saraswati ghat S1, Near Bade Hanuman mandir ghat S2, Ramghat S3, Sangum Chetra S4. The study among all these phytoplanktonic algae, Bacillariophyceae was recorded as a dominant class in Ganga River at Allahabad. Result shows that diversity of species Bacillariophyceae 41.75%, Cyanophyceae 18.95%, Chlorophyceae 40.12%, Euglenophyceae 7.04% were composed.

Keywords Phytoplanktonic Algae, Vegetation, Bacillariophyceae.

Introduction

The word plankton originates from the Greek word for "wandering." It refers to the astonishingly diverse group of plants and animals that spend some or all of their life cycle drifting in the water of oceans or freshwater lakes. Although many of these organisms are capable of locomotion, they are generally unable to move independently of currents and waves. This lack of strong swimming ability separates plankton from nekton, which includes organisms that can control their movement in the water (such as fish). Some planktonic organisms can be quite large (up to a meter or more), however, plankton is generally smaller than nekton, and most are best viewed with the aid of a microscope. (Prescott 1969).

Objective of study A study was carried out highlighting the role of changing water condition in determining the abundance and succession of phytoplanktons.

Review of Literature Phytoplankton is often an important link in the transformation of energy in ecosystem. Phytoplankton plays an important role to make climax community. Phytoplankton is indicator to pioneer community. Rivers are the major sources of drinking water, besides their usages in agriculture, washing, bathing etc. (Palharya and Malviya 1988, Mahajan 1988). In all rivers there are seasonal changes in abundance, there is a minimum algae in winters and maximum in spring and autumn, the 2 maximal caused by different species. There are different species in oligotrophic and eutrophic waters in the former especially near the source many sp are characteristics, although they may be scarce, but one nearly always finds the diatoms Eunotia spp, Achnanthes spp and Diatoma haemale and often Ceratoneis and Tabellaria spp and members of Chaetophorales. As one proceeds downstream the water becomes more eutrophic and the algal community changes until it becomes dominated by the diatom Cocconeis placentula, and the green algae Chamaesiphon. Several other species of diatom are also present. These include Synedra ulna, Navicula viridula, Surirella ovate, Cymbella ventricosa and Gomphonema olivaceum. (Kalpana Srivastava et al. , 2022)

Sampling The phytoplankton's samples were collected from four different sampling sties in ganga river in sterile glass bottles. Sample were analysed frequently and seasonally time to time with respect to the first sample

collected with the help of Advanced laboratory microscope. Samples are collected time to time through natural habitats following S1, S2, S3, S4 respectively. The systematic identification of planktons was made by Fritch 1916, Desikachary 1959. Water samples were collected from four sampling sites in Ganga River at Prayagraj. Counting of the individual plankton was done by 'Lac keys' dropping method (1935). Using the following formula.

$$\text{Plankton units/Liter} = \frac{N \times C \times 10}{Y}$$

Here,

- N = Number of plankton counted in 0.1 ml concentrate.
- C = Total volume of concentrate in ml.
- Y = Total volume of water filtered for sample in liters

The plankton density was expressed on individuals/liter.

But in filamentous algae viz. *Cladophora glomerata*, *Oedogonium sp.*, *Spirogyra sp.*, *Ulothrix sp.*, *Zygnema sp.*, *Chara sp.* among the members of Chlorophyceae and *Nostoc muscorum*, *Anabaena sp.*, *Oscillatoria limosa*, survival of green filamentous and unicellular algae showed better survival rate than blue green algae rather than Diatoms too. (Adoni 1985).

Physical Properties of Ganga Water

pH of river Ganga varied from 7.1 to 9.6. It was observed that the pH of water was found to be higher mostly during monsoon period. An acceptable pH for drinking water is specified as 6.5-8.5. The dissolved oxygen (DO) varied from 4.1 to 6.5 mg in monsoon and 5.4 to 8.2 mg in post monsoon season.

Result and Discussion

The planktonic algal forms belong to, Chlorophyceae, Cyanophyceae, Bascillariophyceae and Euglenophyceae. The availability of phytoplankton in the riverine ecosystem depends upon its physiographic. Reduced number of phytoplankton had been reported from acidic water and it was supported by Lewitus et al (1998). The maximum phytoplankton population found in post monsoon; it may be due to the favourable condition of the water supported by its physical properties. Howland (1929). In monsoon season the population was low, probability due to increased rainfall, increase turbidity runoff and dilution effect due to flood. (Srivastava 1999).

S.N.	Group/Genera	Phytoplankton	Sampling Sites			
			S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄
BACILLARIOPHYCEAE <i>Navicula grimmei</i>	Summer (water temperature 29±1°C)	+++	++	+	++	
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++	
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+	-	-	+	
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++++	++++	+++	++	
<i>Nitschgia palea</i>	Summer (water temperature 29±1°C)	+++	+++	++	++	
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++	++++	+++	
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+	+	-	-	
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++++	++++	++	+++	

<i>Synedra sp.</i>	Summer (water temperature 29±1°C)	++++	+++	++++	++
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++	++++	++
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	++	++	+	+
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++	++	++	++
B. CHLOROPHYCEAE					
1 <i>Cladophora glomerata</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C)	+++++	+++++	++++	+++
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++++	++++	+++
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+	+	+	+
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++++	+++++	++++	++++
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++	+++	+++	+
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
<i>Cosmarium granatum</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C)	+++	++	++	+
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+	+	+	+
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	-	-	-	-
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	++	++	++	+
<i>Oedogonium sp</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C)	++	++	++	++
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+	+	+	+
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
<i>Spirogyra sp.</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C)	++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++++	++++	+++++
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++++	+++	+++	++++
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
<i>Ulothrix sp.</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++	+++	+++	+++
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	++	++	++	++
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
<i>Volvox sp.</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C)	+++++	+++++	++++	++++
	Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
	Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
	Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++++	+++++	++++	++++

	<i>Zygnema sp.</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C))	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
	<i>Chara sp.</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C))	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++	+++	+++	+++
		Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
C. CYANOPHYCEAE						
	<i>Nostoc muscorum</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C))	++	++	++	++
		Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	++++	+++	+++	+++
		Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
	<i>Oscillatoria limosa</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C))	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	++++	++++	++++	++++
		Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
	<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C))	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	++++	++++	+++	+++
		Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++++	+++++	+++++	+++++
		Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	+++	+++	+++	+++
D. EUGLENOPHYCEAE						
	<i>Euglena ignobilis</i>	Summer (water temperature (29±1°C))	++++	++++	++++	++++
		Spring (water temperature 26±1°C)	++++	+++	+++	+++
		Rainy (water temperature 25±1°C)	+++	++	++	++
		Winter (water temperature 22±1°C)	++	++	++	++

Note: Summer season-May to August
Spring season-October to November, February to April first week
Rainy Season -July to September
Winter season-Last week of October to Mid of February
Chlorophyceae> Cyanophyceae > Bacillariophyceae ≥ Euglenophyceae

Conclusion

Therefore, from the above study it is concluded that members of Chlorophyceae were dominant in Ganga River at Prayagraj mainly *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Volvox*, *Spirogyra*, *Ulothrix*, *Zygnema*, *Chara* in almost every season and they showed vegetative survival too. Besides this, the members of Cyanophyceae were also found abundantly in Ganga water in almost every season on their sites studied (Ali et al 2009). *Oscillatoria limosa* and *Spirulina platensis* showed better availability and percentage vegetative and reproductive survival in almost every season at each sites studied. Overall, the total phytoplankton count. /ml. is minimum in rainy season and maximum in spring, summer and winter in Ganga River Prayagraj. (Apha 1985, Verma et al.2013, Wetzel 2001, Edmondson 1959).

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